

MODAL ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH STRUCTURES WITH VISCOELASTIC LAYERS

C. Leclerc¹, E.R Fotsing^{1*}, A. Ross¹

¹ CREPEC, Chair on Composites of High Performance (CCHP), Department of Mechanical Engineering, École Polytechnique de Montréal, Montreal, Canada.

* Corresponding author (edith-roland.fotsing@polymtl.ca)

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1 Introduction

Composite sandwich structures are made of a thick and lightweight core, inserted between two thin skins. The low density core can be foam or a honeycomb structure made of metallic or non-metallic material. The skins usually consist of metal or composite laminates and are bonded to the core using an adhesive. Sandwich structures are used increasingly in the aeronautic, automotive, maritime and other industries due to their good mechanical properties and their low mass. For instance, fuselage, parts of the wings and interior design are a few applications for this type of structure in the aeronautic industry.

The skins provide good stiffness, both in-plane and for bending, whereas the core presents good compressive and shear properties. However, those properties also bring a significant drawback, that is, good transmission of both mechanical and acoustic vibration. Vibrations are usually unwanted, as they can possibly cause mechanical damage, such as delamination, or discomfort. Therefore, research is conducted to improve the damping of sandwich structures.

Increased damping can be obtained by active or passive means [1]. Active damping systems use actuators and sensors, therefore require a power source, while passive damping consists of a modification to the internal structure of the material.

One of the most widely used passive damping methods consist of partially or completely covering the structure with a constrained viscoelastic layer (constrained layer damping, CLD) [1] [2] [3]. A promising application of the CLD method for composite sandwich structure with laminated skins

is to add layers of viscoelastic materials between skin plies [4] [5] [6]. Different strategies can be developed. The viscoelastic layers can cover the entire structure for maximal damping, therefore adding significant weight. For a better damping performance over added weight ratio, partial coverage can be achieved by targeting vibration nodes, where shear stress is maximum. As each vibration mode has its own nodes, the number of partial viscoelastic patches, as well as their length and position, must be optimized. In previous work, the damping of such composite structures was studied, and improved damping performance was observed [4]. While complete coverage usually performs best, significant increase in damping can be reached with partial coverage, resulting in much less added mass [7] [8].

This work deals with the modal analysis of composite sandwich beams with full and partial viscoelastic layers interleaved in the face sheets. The vibration response of the cantilever beams was obtained experimentally using a laser vibrometer. The damping performance was measured using a modified curve fitting method in order to compare the efficiency of different passive treatments. One of the secondary objectives was to verify the validity of the modified curve fitting as a method to obtain modal properties of composite sandwich structures. This method was combined to the half-power bandwidth method in order to improve the measurement accuracy of the structural damping.

2 Experimental procedures

2.1 Beams manufacturing

Sandwich panels were made of an aramid honeycomb core and prepreg carbon/epoxy fabric skins in $[0/45/45/0]_s$ stacking sequence. They were manufactured using an autoclave under controlled temperature and pressure following an aeronautic procedure. Each panel was $400 \times 400 \text{ mm}^2$, with a thickness of 14.3 mm. From those panels, eight $300 \times 30 \text{ mm}^2$ beam samples were cut. The honeycomb cells at the clamped end were filled with resin loaded with glass bubbles over a length of 50 mm to increase local stiffness as shown on Figure 1. To improve damping performance, some of the samples had a thin viscoelastic material inserted between face sheet plies, at symmetric locations with respect to the neutral axis of the beam. The viscoelastic layer was placed close to the honeycomb core, between the third and fourth plies of each face sheet. This location was chosen to have the damping layer as close as possible to the neutral axis of the beam where shearing is maximal.

Figure 2 shows the stacking sequence for beams with or without viscoelastic treatment. The location of the damping treatment along the beam axis is shown on Figure 3, and the positions with respect to the clamping area are listed in Table 1. The viscoelastic material used was the 0.2 mm thick Smacwrap ST film from SMAC. Three beams with one pair of 50 mm-long partial viscoelastic patches and two beams with full viscoelastic layer in each skin were manufactured. It should be noted that the interleaved viscoelastic layers were 28 mm wide leaving 1 mm edges at each side of the insert, in order to avoid side effects. Three reference beams (with no treatment) were also made for comparison purposes.

2.2 Testing parameters

Vibration response due to external excitation and damping efficiency are usually measured using accelerometers bonded directly to the structure [4] [6]. However, the presence of accelerometers is proven to modify the beam response. Contact measurement leads to increased mass, resulting in frequency shift, and additional damping due to

wiring. An alternative consists of using a laser vibrometer which is a non-contact measurement method based on the Doppler principle. Using this method the displacement or the velocity can be measured in the time domain with high precision and without any influence on the vibrational characteristics of the test specimen

The samples were vertically clamped at one end using a dedicated test bench. A clamping protocol was developed to assure constant boundary conditions for every test. Four bolts were tightened with a torque of 6 N·m to secure the clamping block. The beams were excited using an instrumented impact hammer (PCB Piezotronics, model 086C01), and transient vibration data was acquired using a laser vibrometer (Polytec, sensor head OFV-505, controller OFV-5000) coupled with a velocity decoder (Polytec, VD-06). The impact point was 20 mm above the clamped end, whereas the measurement point was 55 mm below the free end. Figure 4 shows a schema of the experimental set up.

2.3 Modal analysis

The determination of the structural damping can be made through different methods. The logarithmic decrement is frequently used [9] for underdamped system. When the system becomes overdamped other methods such as the half-power bandwidth method (3dB method) [10] can be used. However, to increase the accuracy of damping measurement the use of modified curve fitting algorithm [11] combined with the 3dB method is sometimes necessary.

Each sample was tested twice, each test consisting of 20 impacts using the impact hammer. A root mean square averaging method was applied to the data to improve the reliability. Both natural frequencies and damping ratios were obtained using the Frequency Response Function (FRF). The FRF was computed using a Fast Fourier Transform algorithm.

A method was developed to obtain the modal properties of sandwich composite beams. A modified curve fitting algorithm based on the mobility equation of a single degree of freedom (SDOF) system (equation 1) [12] was used. A linear scale is used for the amplitude of the FRF, as the

curve fitting method was implemented in the linear form of the FRF.

$$\left| \frac{V(\omega)}{F(\omega)} \right| = \frac{\omega \frac{\omega_n^2}{k}}{\sqrt{(\omega_n^2(1 - \zeta) - \omega^2)^2 + (2\zeta\omega\omega_n)^2}} \quad (1)$$

This equation presents 3 unknowns, which are the stiffness coefficient (k), the natural frequency (ω_n) and the damping ratio (ζ). As this equation is for a SDOF system, fitting was done on each modal peak individually, optimizing the 3 unknown parameters of the equation with the nonlinear least squares method.

Once the damping ratio obtained, the loss factor (η) was calculated using the following expression.

$$\eta = 2\zeta \quad (2)$$

3 Results and discussions

To validate the experimental set up, the experimental procedure and the curve fitting method, preliminary tests were made. The same beam was successively tested three times. The set up was disassembled between each test run. Modal analysis was made and results for natural frequencies and loss factors were compared. For each mode, relative differences on natural frequencies remained under 1%, while relative differences on loss factors stayed under 7%.

Figure 5 shows a typical experimental FRF obtained with peaks corresponding to the first 6 vibration modes. It can be seen that the non-contact measurement led to a frequency response with few noise.

Figure 6 presents an experimental peak and the numerically obtained fitting curve corresponding to Equation (1). The optimized fitting parameters are also given on Figure 6. It can be seen that the fitted curve is in very good agreement with the experimental points.

The main disadvantage of the curve fitting method is the use of a SDOF equation, while the tested specimens correspond to multiple degree of freedom (MDOF) systems. For lightly damped structures, the modal peaks are narrow and coupling

is negligible. But as soon as damping increases, peaks become wider and overlap noticeably. As coupling effect is not included in the curve fitting method, the fitted curve does not coincide perfectly with the experimental points. Figure 7a shows an example of this phenomenon.

A comparison of the curve fitting method and the well-known half-power bandwidth method was made. However, the use of this second method requires a well-defined peak. For a narrow peak such as the one corresponding to the first mode, the experimental points do not shape the summit well enough for a precise estimation of the damping. This problem is solved by using the curve fitting as shown on Figure 7b. As the half-power bandwidth need a precise estimation of the maximal response to calculate damping, a peak as shown on figure 7b does not allow a reliable estimation of the loss factor. Furthermore, experimental errors can have a significant influence on the half-power bandwidth method, while the curve fitting, using a least squares method, does not have the same sensibility.

The natural frequencies and loss factors for the first 5 modes of each beam were obtained with both methods. Relative differences with respect to half-power bandwidth were calculated to compare the results. Differences for natural frequencies (not shown) were negligible (usually under 0.2%). Table 2 shows loss factors obtained with both methods for 2 different beams. While the two methods present similar loss factors for the reference beam (reference 1), differences can be seen for the beam with complete treatment (complete 1). Indeed, the difference for the third, fourth and fifth mode is not negligible. The absolute difference between loss factors values for the three last modes is constant and around 0.55%. However the curve fitting tend to give higher loss factors for higher modes. Table 3 presents the natural frequencies and loss factors for the five first modes of eight experimental beams obtained using the curve fitting method. Figure 8a shows a comparison of the loss factors only. It can be seen that damping is usually more important for higher modes (see Figure 8a). The increasing loss factor with increasing frequency is observed for both methods.

Full coverage of the beam with a viscoelastic layer greatly improves damping; it also significantly increases the mass of the beam. Therefore, a 4% decrease of the natural frequencies is observed from

the reference beams to the beams with complete damping treatment. A well-positioned single patch also increases damping significantly, but with minor impact on natural frequencies.

For all modes, results show that a patch placed near the clamping area (Visco P0) is most effective to improve damping performance. Indeed, energy dissipation in the viscoelastic material is proportional to shear stress, which is maximal in this area. Local maxima are obtained not only at the clamping area, but also at vibration nodes. For this reason, aside from the clamping area, patches that coincide with a vibration node have greater effect on the corresponding mode. To illustrate this, node positions for a similar beam was measured previously for the first four modes [4]. The node for the second mode is located at 185 mm. Nodes for the third mode are located at 105 mm and 210 mm. Finally nodes for the fourth mode are located at 70 mm, 145 mm and 215 mm. Given these node positions, damping of the third mode is increased with patch P2 (placed 80 mm from the clamping area), while damping of the fourth mode is increased with patch P1 (40mm from the clamping area). Figure 9 shows an illustration of vibration nodes and patches locations. Furthermore, damping for the fifth mode is almost equally increased for both locations P1 and P2, suggesting that each patch coincides with a vibration node. Figure 8b illustrates these results. It can be seen that damping for beam Visco P2 increases significantly from mode 2 to mode 3, while the increment between modes 3 and 4 is very small. The opposite can be seen for beam Visco P1, where the increment in damping between modes 2 and 3 is smaller, and the increment between mode 3 and 4 is important.

It should be remembered that patches are only 50 mm long. Extrapolating from above, one might expect that the patches are more likely to influence the damping of the mode with the nearest node. When no node coincides with a patch, damping is comparable to what is observed on the reference beams. Position P1 for the third mode and position P2 for the fourth mode reflect this situation. Trends seen in the present study are in agreement with previously published results [4].

The damping due to a single patch treatment is always greater than the damping of the reference beam. Moreover the performance of both treatments (single patch and full coverage) increases with

increasing frequencies. However the effect of single treatment becomes less important for higher modes when compared to full coverage. Indeed for the first mode, beam with patch placed near the clamping area (Visco P0) and beam with full coverage treatment show similar damping.

3 Conclusions

Modal analysis from non-contact laser vibrometer measurements leads to frequency response function without noise. Damping ratio can be determined reliably by curve fitting each frequency peak to a SDOF response spectrum. This method helps solving some problems encountered with the half-power bandwidth method for lightly damped structures, such as poorly define peak. Moreover this method led to higher loss factors compared to the half-power bandwidth method. This can be explained by the use of the SDOF equation that does not take into account the modal coupling effect often seen in heavily damped structures. It was shown that patches placed adequately (clamping area or mode node) along the beam axis improve the loss factor by 50% for low frequency modes and by 30 % for higher modes. With respect to the full coverage treatment, the single patch leads to lower damping performance but reduces significantly the added mass.

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Figure 1: Geometry of the sandwich composite beam

Figure 2: Stacking sequence without treatment (a) and with viscoelastic layers (b)

Figure 3: Illustration of the patch position

Table 1: Position of the viscoelastic patches for each beam

Damping treatment position	P0	P1	P2
Distance of the patch, D (mm)	0	40	80

Figure 4: Experimental set-up

Figure 5: A typical FRF obtained in the experiments

Figure 6: Examples of a good curve fit
 Parameters: $\omega_n=767.9$ Hz ; $\zeta=0.00703$; $k=12931$ N/m

a)

b)

Figure 7: Examples of a peak with a heavily damped peak (a) and a lack of point near its summit (b)

Table 2: Comparison of the half-power bandwidth and curve fitting methods

	Method	Beam	
		Reference 1	Complete 1
Mode 1	η (%) (Half-Power)	1,28	2,28
	η (%) (Curve fitting)	1,26	2,18
	Relative difference (%)	-1,71	-4,52
Mode 2	η (%) (Half-Power)	1,40	3,00
	η (%) (Curve fitting)	1,41	3,05
	Relative difference (%)	0,34	1,59
Mode 3	η (%) (Half-Power)	1,87	3,61
	η (%) (Curve fitting)	1,95	4,17
	Relative difference (%)	4,26	15,62
Mode 4	η (%) (Half-Power)	2,20	4,16
	η (%) (Curve fitting)	2,29	4,66
	Relative difference (%)	4,19	11,89
Mode 5	η (%) (Half-Power)	2,35	4,63
	η (%) (Curve fitting)	2,42	5,30
	Relative difference (%)	3,10	14,48

Table 3: Natural frequencies and loss factors for all the test specimens

Beam	Mode 1		Mode 2		Mode 3		Mode 4		Mode 5	
	ω_n (Hz)	η (%)								
Reference 1	199	1,26	768	1,41	1544	1,95	2279	2,29	3000	2,42
Reference 2	200	1,25	775	1,39	1551	1,92	2283	2,48	3038	2,61
Visco P0	200	1,96	779	2,08	1556	2,58	2270	2,85	3017	3,11
Visco P1	207	3,13	779	1,59	1560	1,96	2304	2,78	3056	2,94
Visco P2	199	1,34	766	1,51	1556	2,26	2278	2,43	3037	2,95
Complete 1	189	2,18	725	3,05	1458	4,17	2145	4,66	2848	5,30
Complete 2	194	2,17	739	2,87	1490	3,96	2177	4,22	2875	5,18

a)

b)

Figure 8: Comparison of loss factors for each treatment, group by mode (a) and by treatment (b)

Figure 9: Nodes positions for the first 4 modes, with patches locations

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